

Video S1: Two *Nematodinium* sp. cells (Nm-QI1, Nm-QI2). Cells are pigmented green. Nm-QI1 is in a non-motile, possibly encysted state with a single moving flagellum. Cell Nm-QI2 is in the process of dividing, with dissociated ocelloid components partitioned into each daughter cell. A single nematocyst-like extrusome is visible in Nm-QI1 (indicated by an arrow) but none are visible in Nm-QI2.

Video S2: Two *Erythrospidium* sp. cells (Er-QI1, Er-QI2). Er-QI1 lacks a characteristic piston or any moving flagella. The compartmentalization of the pink pigment, the globular form of both the hyalosome and the retinal body of the ocelloid, and the central position of the ocelloid in the cell are consistent with an early stage of cell division. In contrast, Er-QI2 is in the trophont stage with diffuse pigment, an anteriorly positioned ocelloid, and a piston appendage covered with spine-like protrusions. It has a fin-like episomal extension at its anterior end, around which faint movement of a transverse flagellum can be seen.

Video S3: Four *Warnowia* sp. cells (Wa-QI1, Wa-QI2, Wa-QI3, Wa-QI4). All cells lack pigment other than dark ocelloid plastids. *Warnowia* cells are slightly longer than *Proterothropsis* and more uniform in width, with a long cingulum encircling two full times, spiraling from top to three quarters of the way down the cell. The ocelloid is located just posterior to the cell midpoint. A blunt anterior protrusion is visible on the episome of cells Wa-QI1 and Wa-QI2. Wa-QI3 is in the process of dividing with two fully formed ocelloids localized to the developing daughter cells. Nematocysts are not visible in any *Warnowia* cells collected in this study.

Video S4: Eight *Proterothropsis* sp. cells (Pr-FC1, Pr-FC2, Pr-FC3, Pr-FC4, Pr-QI5, Pr-QI6, Pr-QI7, Pr-QI8). Pr-FC1 appears different from all other *Proterothropsis* collected here, with a more pointed cell shape, suggesting it is a different species. Two cells are in different states of division – the ocelloid retinal body in Pr-QI5 is elongated in preparation for division, while in Pr-QI7 the mostly-differentiated daughter cells each contain their own ocelloid components. The squat shape of Pr-QI6 suggests it is likely the product of recent division. All other cells are similar in shape. Internal structures consistent with the size and shape of nematocyst-like extrusomes are visible in all cells (indicated with arrows) except Pr-FC1 and Pr-FC3. Some cells appear to have faint peripheral patches of greenish pigmentation, most pronounced in cell Pr-QI7.

Video S5: Eight *Polykrikos kofoidii* cells (Pk-FC1, Pk-FC2, Pk-FC3, Pk-FC4, Pk-FC5, Pk-FC6, Pk-FC7, Pk-QI8). Pk-FC1 and Pk-FC3 have angular, accordion-like strobila with pronounced infoldings between zooids and sharp cingulum ridges that protrude as the widest points along the cell. Pk-FC4 and Pk-FC2 have a similar shape, but are more swollen with much shallower infoldings. In cells Pk-FC6 and Pk-FC5 the creases between zooids are so shallow that they are nearly flush. The shape of Pk-FC7 cannot be discerned because the cell is oriented in a vertical position, but it is notably diffuse pink in color. The most morphologically divergent cell is Pk-QI8, in which zooids are nearly spherical in shape, strung together in a tight curve. Nematocyst-like extrusomes are observed in all cells, most with visible taeniocyst attachments.

Video S6: Two *Cyklopsia* sp. cells (Cy-JP1, Cy-FC2). The morphology of these cells did not resemble descriptions of known warnowiid species. At approximately 40 μm in length, *Cyklopsia* is notably smaller than all other warnowiids collected in this study. The *Cyklopsia* ocelloid is similar in size to those of *Proterothropsis*, causing the organelle to appear large relative to the cell. Unlike the opaque, nearly black retinal bodies of the other warnowiids, those of *Cyklopsia* are a translucent red. Nematocyst-like extrusomes are visible in Cy-FC2, indicated by arrows. A structure resembling a nematocyst can be seen

partially obscured by the ocelloid in Cy-JP1 but cannot be confirmed due to constant motion of the cell. During observation, Cy-FC2 anchors itself to the vessel surface by what appears to be two flagella-like strands with sticky ends. Whether these appendages are flagella or tethers extending from extrusomes can not be determined. The two Cyklopsia cells are very similar in shape and size with notable differences between their morphologies. The more bulbous episome of Cy-JP1 is pronounced and wider than the tapered posterior end of the cell, while the episome of Cy-FC2 is smaller and similar in width to the rest of the cell. Cell Cy-JP1 has a wing-like extension at its posterior end that is absent in Cy-FC2.